

1:3-PROPANEDIOLS AND THEIR DERIVATIVES

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2:2-Disubstituted 1:3-propanediols have been synthesised and characterised by preparing their urethanes. Diethyl-aminoethyl ethers of the diols have also been reported.

Most known antihistaminic compounds contain a quaternary carbon atom. This paper describes the preparation of 2:2-disubstituted 1:3-propanediols and their diethylaminoethyl ethers.

Shortridge *et al.* (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, 70, 948) have prepared 2:2-dimethyl-1:3-propanediol and 2:2-diethyl-1:3-propanediol by condensing formaldehyde with appropriate butyraldehyde in the presence of alkali; while 2:2-dibutyl-1:3-propanediol was obtained by Bouveault and Blanc (*Bull. Soc. Chim.*, 1904, iii, 31, 1205) by the reduction of dibutylmalonic ester with sodium and ethanol. 1:3-Propanediols described in this work were prepared by lithium aluminium hydride reduction of the disubstituted malonates. The yields were 50 to 60%. These diols have been characterised by the preparation of their phenylurethanes. The diethyl-aminoethyl ethers have been prepared by the interaction of diethylaminoethyl chloride and sodio derivatives of glycols, prepared in benzene.

Reduction of diethyl dipropylmalonate to the related glycol could not be carried out due to complications arising probably (?) by the removal of one propyl group during the reduction.

EXPERIMENTAL

All the required substituted malonates were prepared by alkylation of diethyl malonate in the presence of sodium ethoxide using standard procedure.

Diethyl Ester of Methyl-dodecylmalonic Acid.—This ester was prepared by the action of methyl iodide on sodio derivative of diethyl dodecylmalonate, b.p. 187°/4 mm. (Found: C, 69.3; H, 11.9. $C_{19}H_{38}O_4$ requires C, 69.5; H, 11.0%).

2-Methyl-2-dodecylpropanediol.— $LiAlH_4$ (2.5 g.) was suspended in dry ether (125 c.c.) and the solution of the ester (16.4 g., 0.05 M) in dry ether (50 c.c.) was added to it in small lots in about 2 hrs. with stirring. The reaction mixture was further refluxed for 5 hrs., cooled in ice and decomposed by dropwise addition of water (25 c.c.), and the ether layer (A) was removed. The residual white precipitate was dissolved by sulphuric acid and was extracted with ether (3 × 25 c.c.). The ether extract after washing with sodium bicarbonate and finally with water was added to the ether layer (A). The combined ether extract was dried over magnesium sulphate, filtered and the solvent removed, when a white solid was obtained. It was crystallised from petroleum ether (60–80°) as white needles, m.p. 63–65°, yield 8 g. (Found: C, 73.7; H, 13.2. $C_{15}H_{32}O_2$ requires C, 73.7; H, 13.2%). Its diphenylurethane had m.p. 74–75°. (Found: N, 5.7. $C_{29}H_{42}O_4N_2$ requires N 5.8%).

The same method was followed for the reduction of all the remaining alkyl malonates, and the 1:3-propanediols were characterised by preparing their diphenylurethanes.

Diethylaminoethyl Ether of 2-Methyl-2-dodecyl-1:3-propanediol.—Diethylaminoethyl chloride was obtained from its hydrochloride (Breslow *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1944, 66, 1922) by suspending it in benzene and treating the suspension with an excess of sodium hydroxide. The benzene

TABLE I

S. No.	Name (D=1:3-propanediol)	Formula.	M. P.	B. P.	Yield	% Carbon. Found. Calc.	% Hydrogen. Found. Calc.	% Nitrogen. Found. Calc.
1.	2,2-Dimethyl-D	$C_5H_{12}O_2$	127° (lit. 127°)	108-11°	21%			
2.	DPU of (1)	$C_{10}H_{18}O_4N_2$	141-42°	3.5 mm	81			8.0 8.1
3.	DEAE of (1)	$C_{11}H_{19}O_3N$	..	..	25			6.8 6.9
4.	2,2-Diethyl-D	$C_7H_{14}O_2$	61.5° (lit. 61°)	..	Plates from pet. ether			
5.	DPU of (4)	$C_{20}H_{38}O_4N_2$	110°	140-45°	83			7.7 7.5
6.	DEAE of (4)	$C_{19}H_{36}O_3N$	..	..	25			5.9 6.0
7.	2,2-Dipropyl-D	$C_9H_{18}O_2$	59°	7 mm	89	67.3 67.5	12.6 12.5	
8.	DPU of (7)	$C_{20}H_{38}O_4N_2$	144-45°	..	Needles			6.8 7.0
9.	DEAE of (7)	$C_{19}H_{36}O_3N$	..	147-52°	..			5.2 5.4
10.	2-Propyl-D	$C_8H_{16}O_2$	..	4.5 mm	19	60.3 61.0	12.2 11.9	
11.	DPU of (10)	Could not be obtained pure.	..	151-56°	..			
12.	DEAE of (10)	$C_{13}H_{24}O_3N$	..	37 mm	40			6.1 6.4
13.	2,2-Dibutyl-D	$C_{11}H_{22}O_2$	..	6 mm	28	70.0 70.2	12.5 12.7	
14.	DPU of (13)	$C_{20}H_{38}O_4N_2$	145°	..	Needles			6.6 6.5
15.	DEAE of (13)	$C_{19}H_{36}O_3N$	..	155-60°	40			4.6 4.8
16.	2,2-Dibutyl-D	$C_{11}H_{22}O_2$	75-76°	3 mm	38			
				153-57°				
				9 mm				

TABLE I (contd.)

S. No.	Name (D=1:3-propanediol)	Formula.	M. P.	B. P. (Lit-155-60°)	Yield	% Carbon. Found. Calc.	% Hydrogen. Found. Calc.	% Nitrogen. Found. Calc.
16.				20 mm				
17.	DPU of (16)	$C_{12}H_{16}O_4N_2$	154-55°	..	..	..	..	6.3 6.5
18.	DEAE of (16)	$C_{11}H_{15}O_3N$	..	165-70° 3 mm	30	..	..	4.8 4.8
19.	2:2-Dihexyl-D	$C_{18}H_{28}O_2$	..	185-86° 4-5 mm	60	73.5 73.7	13.1 13.1	
20.	DPU of (19)	$C_{20}H_{28}O_4N_2$	123-24°	..	Needles	..	..	5.8 5.8
21.	DEAE of (19)	$C_{19}H_{26}O_3N$	..	165-70° 4 mm	30	..	..	3.8 4.0
22.	2:2-Dihexyl-D	$C_{18}H_{28}O_2$	..	167-72°	34	75.8 76.0	12.9 13.1	
23.	DPU of (22)	$C_{20}H_{28}O_4N_2$	85-86°	..	Needles	..	..	5.0 5.2
24.	DEAE of (22)	$C_{19}H_{26}O_3N$	..	245-50° 3 mm	36	..	..	3.9 4.0
25.	2:2-Dibenzyl-D	$C_{17}H_{18}O_2$	..	230-60° 5 mm	31	79.8 79.7	8.0 7.8	
26.	DPU of (25)	$C_{19}H_{26}O_4N_2$	190-91°	..	..	..	..	5.7 5.6
27.	DEAE of (25)	$C_{18}H_{24}O_3N$	..	230-35° 7 mm	40	..	..	3.8 3.9
28.	2:2-Dihexyl-D	$C_{18}H_{28}O_2$	..	165-70° 4 mm	15	75.8 76.0	5.6 13.3	
29.	DPU of (28)	$C_{20}H_{28}O_4N_2$	118-19°	..	..	..	..	5.6 5.8

extract was dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate, filtered, concentrated, and the oil was used as such for further reaction. The condensation of the chloride with the glycol was carried out as follows.

2-Methyl-2-dodecyl-1 : 3-propanediol (3.66 g., 0.015 *M*) was added to powdered sodium (0.35 g., 0.015 *M*) in thiophene-free benzene (10 c.c.). The mixture was refluxed on a water bath for 4 hrs. till sodium had dissolved, and the resulting solution was cooled. Diethylaminoethyl chloride in benzene was added to the solution and the mixture was refluxed for about 40 hrs. and cooled. The benzene layer was separated, washed with water, and dried over sodium sulphate. The residue obtained after removal of the benzene was distilled under reduced pressure, b.p. 195-200°/1.5 mm, yield 1.0 g. (about 20%).

1 : 3-Propanediols, their phenylurethane derivatives (denoted as DPU) and their diethylaminoethyl ethers (denoted as DEAE) are reported in Table I.

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